

CESSDA Work Plan 2020

CESSDA Widening Activities and Journals Outreach 2020

Deliverable D9 Report from the Local Event in Poland

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Executive summary

The principal aims of the CESSDA local event are to promote the development of sustainable national data archives, as well as collaboration and a possible membership in CESSDA. The local event targets both users of the data archives in the country and important national stakeholders (research institutions, funders, ministries, etc.).

The CESSDA event in Poland was originally planned on the 2nd of April 2020 in face-to-face mode, but was postponed and changed due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The event took place online on the 18th of March 2021. Overall, the CESSDA local event in Poland was a success as it reached a wide audience composed of potential data depositors and data users, as well as data librarians and management's representatives of more than 30 research institutions active in social sciences and other research fields. ADJ and PADS, the Polish archives for respectively qualitative and quantitative social science data, had the opportunity to present their services. In addition, the EU research landscape was presented and the importance for a country such as Poland to get organised in order to join ERICs and EOSC was emphasised. Most panellists supported the development of national social science data archives in Poland. The roundtable discussion also brought out a misapprehension about the specificities of social sciences data compared to data in other research fields.

This reveals the importance of gathering researchers, data professionals and funders from different fields. Such events give the opportunity to inform all stakeholders about social sciences data's specific needs and the presence of CESSDA provides extra strength to the position of local data archives. This is certainly the reason why local events are so in demand at CESSDA partners (i.e., data archives that are aiming to join CESSDA). The general concept presented in this document could be used to organise new local events in other countries.

Abbreviations and acronyms

ADJ	Polish Social Science Archive for Qualitative Data
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CESSDA DMEG	CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide
CESSDA MO	CESSDA Main Office
CSDA	Czech Social Science Data Archive
CBOS	Public Opinion Research Center (Poland)
DMP	Data Management Plan
DROBD	Domain-Specific Repositories for Research Data (Poland)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable and Reproducible
FORS	Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences
GESIS	Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences (Germany)
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICM	Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling
ICPSR	Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (USA)
IFiS PAN	Institute of Philosophy and Sociology of the Polish Academy of Sciences
NCN	National Science Center Poland
PADS	Polish Social Science Archive for Quantitative Data
SP(s)	Service Provider(s)
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
WA 2019	Widening Activities 2019
WAO 2020	Widening Activities and Outreach 2020

Introduction

The idea to organise a local event (also called national event) on data research infrastructure for social sciences in a CESSDA non-member country was first developed in early 2019 and was included as an additional subtask to the CESSDA Work Plan 'Widening Activities 2019' (WA 2019). WA 2019 began in January 2019 and finished in March 2020.

The local event was named and developed in addition to the CESSDA Widening events also organised by the CESSDA Widening Activities team over the last years and that gather together representatives of different CESSDA members Service Providers (SPs) and CESSDA partners (i.e., data archives that are aiming to join CESSDA). The aim of this local event is to bring together key partners for the sustainable development of a national data archive and users of this archive (that is mainly the researchers and students) to exchange ideas on how to implement it, all under the umbrella and facilitation of CESSDA. The focus is thus on a specific national context, contrary to the CESSDA Widening events.

CESSDA local event

The concept

The local event is organised by the local partner institution(s) in cooperation with the CESSDA Widening Activities team. CESSDA supports the event by the participation of CESSDA MO representative(s) and selected CESSDA expert(s). The event will target both, (1) researchers and (potential) users of data archives in the country and (2) important national stakeholders (funders, university/academy, research infrastructures, etc.). The intention is to promote the development of local data archives and the data sharing culture, as well as increase CESSDA visibility and promote the collaboration and a possible membership with CESSDA.

The typical programme of a local event is constituted of a core part and additional modules that can be included or not, based upon the local needs and stakeholders' availability. The core programme includes presentations of CESSDA and the local SP(s) as well as a roundtable. This roundtable is the most important part of the programme and should include high level representatives from CESSDA MO, the local SP(s), local research community, local funders, and/or any stakeholders (universities, academy, research institutes...) who can significantly help in developing and institutionalising the data archive.

Additional modules could be in one hand presentations regarding benefits from data sharing, European open access policies, FAIR data, EOSC, etc. In the other hand, additional modules

can also include presentation(s) of CESSDA products, like the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide, or some popular topics related to data management (e.g., GDPR), data archiving, data discovery, data reuse and citation, etc. to make the event more attractive to the local research community. Additional modules may also contribute to objectives of projects organised by the CESSDA Training Working Group.

The core part should be organised over a half-day (e.g., morning session) and additional modules can then take place during the other part of the day. The core part should be a public conference facilitating researchers and students attendance, while the additional modules could target smaller groups. Ideally, the events should be organised in a university. The definitive programme should be developed in close collaboration with the local SP and tailored to local conditions.

Furthermore, the local event provides an opportunity to organise side-meetings between CESSDA, the local SP, and the local funders and decision makers.

Selection of the hosting country

The selection of a hosting country can be based on priorities at CESSDA MO, at the CESSDA Mentorship Programme or based on an open call to CESSDA partners.

CESSDA Data Day in Poland

Choice of Poland

Poland was selected by CESSDA MO as a hosting country for the first local event in late 2019. The Polish team showed great interest in being the centre point of such an event and local archives for social science data are running for a few years. However, the archives lack sustainable fundings.

Organisation of the 2020 event

The organisation of the local event in Poland started in February 2020. The organisation team was composed by colleagues from two CESSDA SPs, FORS and CSDA, and the Polish Social Science Data Archive (PADS) supported by e-infrastructure experts from the Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling (ICM) at the University of Warsaw.

The team met every week from the 6th of February to the 18th of March. During this period, the team prepared a detailed concept for Poland, defined the target audience, defined the programme, prepared and sent first invitations to the presenters, round table speakers and

the audience. The event website and registration form were put online, a communication plan to reach the target audience was ready, and the date, location and catering were booked.

The event was scheduled for the 2nd of April, but due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the organisation team decided, on the 11th of March, to postpone the event to a more convenient date for a face-to-face event and to continue the organisation once the new date was set.

Organisation of the 2021 event

The remaining budget from WA 2019 was moved to the CESSDA Work plan 'Widening Activities and Outreach 2020' (WAO 2020), going from January 2020 to March 2021. As the COVID-19 pandemic prevented a face-to-face event, at the end of 2020, it was decided to organise an online event in early 2021.

The organisation of the local event in Poland started again in January 2021. The organisation team expanded and was composed by Christina Bornatici (FORS), Jindrich Krejci (CSDA) and Ilona Trtíková (CSDA) for CESSDA and by Magdalena Bielińska (IFiS PAN), Wojciech Fenrich (ICM), Piotr Filipkowski (IFiS PAN), Marcin Zieliński (PADS) and Danuta Życzyńska-Ciołek (IFiS PAN) for Poland.

The team met every week from the 26th of January to the 18th of March. The preparatory work carried out in WA 2019 was used to develop the 2021 event. The concept for Poland, the target audience and the programme remained mostly unchanged. The team adapted the invitations, the event website¹ and the registration form², and defined topics and questions for the round table based on the current Polish context and the available speakers. Invitations were sent by the Polish team to relevant institutions and their personal contacts. The Polish team also prepared presentations of their institutions (3 presentations) and the afternoon workshop for students and researchers on research data management. Since the event was online, the team checked different possibilities to host an online event and decided to use the CSDA zoom meeting. Tests were done before the event. It was decided that the event would not be recorded.

The final programme and invitation letters sent to the audience and speakers are available in the annexes.

¹ <http://www.ads.org.pl/cessda-data-day-2021/> (accessed on 13.04.2021)

² https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1HostOtTzr5TF8BLV-42YER2dt8A89j_-qp3U4ufiAvo/edit (accessed on 13.04.2021)

CESSDA Data Day 2021 - Social Science Data Archives in Poland: Opportunities for Researchers and Challenges Ahead

Registration and attendance

Participation was free of charge. In total, 149 people registered for the event, some were interested in the morning and the afternoon sessions and others only in one of them (Figure 1). On the 18th of March, 66 participants took part in the morning session and 35 in the afternoon workshop.

Figure 1: Participants' registration

Among the persons who registered for the event, most of them were data users (35%), followed by representatives of a data service provider (32%, e.g., an archive, a repository, a library; Figure 2). 15% were representatives of a research institution management (e.g., university, funding agency, etc.) or of a state agency, 10% were data producers and 8% students (mostly doctoral students). It should be noted that the registration forms allowed selecting several roles.

Figure 2: Roles of the registered persons

88% of the registered persons were related to Poland and were studying or working at a Polish research institution or at a governmental institution and a Polish representative from the Social and Cultural Innovation Strategy Working Group at ESFRI (Figure 3). 10% were related to CESSDA MO and CESSDA SPs (10 different SPs) and the last 2% represent audiences from other research institutions in Europe and outside Europe.

Figure 3: Institutions of the registered persons

In total, registrants were affiliated to 31 Polish research institutions. The university of Warsaw was the most represented with 28 persons, followed by the Polish Academy of Science (21), the University of Zielony Góra (9), SGH Warsaw School of Economics (7), Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences (5), AMU Poznan (4), University of Lodz (4), Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń (3), SWPS University of Social Sciences and Humanities (3), Pope John Paul II State School of Higher Education in Biała Podlaska (2), University of Silesia in Katowice (2). One person registered from each of the following institutions: Akademia Leona Koźmińskiego, CBOS, Collegium Civitas, IBE-Educational Research Institute, Gdańsk University of Technology, Jagiellonian University, Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce, Kozminski University, Lodz University of Technology Library, NCN, Police Academy in Szczytno, Siedlce University of Natural Sciences and Humanities, Silesian University of Technology, Tadeusz Kościuszko University of Technology, University of Economics and Human Sciences in Warsaw, University of Gdansk, University of Life Sciences in Lublin, University of Opole and University of Strathclyde.

The figures presented above and the list of different Polish research institutions show that the communication about the event reached on one hand the right audience, that is Polish researchers and professionals of data archives, and on the other hand a wide audience from different research institutions and fields in Poland, as well as management of targeted institutions and CESSDA SP colleagues. This also shows that the programme and such local events are appreciated by local researchers and data professionals. The only downside is the lack of representatives from the Polish Ministry in charge of research.³

Minutes of the morning session

9:20 – 9:30: Welcome and introductory presentation

Jindřich Krejčí, Head of CSDA, welcomed the audience, gave technical information about webcams and how to ask questions and briefly presented CESSDA and the event's programme.

9:30 – 10:00 Benefits of joining CESSDA and Data sharing in Europe

Ron Dekker, Director of CESSDA ERIC, presented CESSDA and EOSC. Ron Dekker explained that a research infrastructure like CESSDA is not just a technical tool but has also a human factor. Indeed, CESSDA has a lot to offer thanks to the experts involved and the share of their knowledge (e.g., in teaching and training events) on data archiving, FAIR data, connecting and combining datasets, quality checks of service providers (Core Trust Seal). CESSDA also gives the opportunity to its members to share and access to various data

³ The next teams should make sure to invite well in advance representatives of the Ministry in charge of research.

through its products and tools, and participate with and cooperate in many European projects and infrastructures. There will be a new call in Horizon Europe in May. EOSC is federating the European research infrastructures. CESSDA is a member of EOSC Association and can thus be involved in the development of the EOSC strategy.

10:00 – 10:20: Polish Social Science Archive for Quantitative Data

Marcin W. Zieliński, Head of PADS, presented PADS, the Polish Social Science Archive for Quantitative Data, and explained the importance of archiving research data and where to archive them. Data archiving is required by funders and beneficial for researchers and research in general. For example, it gives possibilities for teaching purposes, reproducibility, new data analysis, long-term preservation, and increase in citations of researcher's work. Data should be archived at domain specific archives using standards for sharing and storing. In Poland, PADS is the only domain archive for quantitative data. PADS was founded in 2003 by social science researchers who were trained in data archiving by ICPSR and GESIS. PADS was established in 2004. There are currently about 100 research projects archived and disseminated. Among the 13,174 users, 64% are students, 84% are academics (i.e., students, researchers, etc.) and 86% are Polish people as data are mostly prepared in Polish language. To reach an international audience, data should be prepared in English as well. Usage statistics also show that among the 70,746 downloads, documentation and metadata are downloaded in much lesser numbers than datasets. The archive needs to improve the students' and researchers' practice. For data depositors, PADS proposes a Handbook of Data Archiving to help data depositors. Also PADS is not a self-archiving system, and each deposit needs approval before publication. The archive controls if the data file is fully described, if there is a methodological description, questionnaires, and the licence agreement. PADS is waiting on the European version of Dataverse (an archiving tool) that is currently developed within CESSDA and SSHOC to adjust to CESSDA requirements. PADS collaborated with CESSDA already in 2004 and renewed its collaboration in 2015. PADS is a member of the CESSDA Trust Working group and has the status of CESSDA partner.

10:20–10:40 Polish Social Science Archive for Qualitative Data

Piotr Filipkowski, Head of ADJ, presented ADJ, the Polish Social Science Archive for Qualitative Data. ADJ was officially established in 2012. Piotr Filipkowski also presented reasons for archiving qualitative data. Researchers collect more data than they are able to analyse, the main goal is reusing and questioning research. One could think of secondary analysis and research revisits (strict ethnographic view, to the same people), historical-methodological reflection. Another goal could be to use original empirical data in academic teaching or to archive data to prevent loss, scattering or destruction. ADJ currently shares about 30 studies. Data types are various. It could be interview transcripts, audio recordings, photos, field notes, first draft of studies, and research documentation

(guidelines, questionnaire). Anonymised data are accessible online, free of charge, for research purposes. ADJ selects data based on a dialogical process of coming to a conclusion if something is worth archiving. It is often a soft and interpretive criteria.

10:40–11:00 New Infrastructure for Opening Social Science Data

Jakub Szprot, Head of the Open Science Platform at Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling (ICM) at University of Warsaw, was replaced by his colleague Wojciech Fenrich. ICM focuses on open access and provides a lot of different materials. ICM is now to develop a Domain-Specific Repositories for Research Data (DROBD) which goal is to prepare and share datasets (mostly from social science). The project has not the aim to create a new repository but to adapt Dataverse to the needs of their partners PADS and ADJ. Dataverse was chosen as it is rich in features and has flexible metadata configuration and management. DROBD should have a Polish and English interface, and possibilities to change metadata (PADS and ADJ should have their own metadata configuration), to assign licence to files, and access should be customised according to the users (but metadata should always be available). Dataverse is used to make data available. Data repository services for individual project purposes without opening access to data are not provided.

11:15 – 12:45: Round table – Sharing Social Science Data in Poland: Which Opportunities and Challenges Ahead? Institutions’ and Researchers’ Perspectives

The round table discussion was moderated by Jindřich Krejčí (Head of CSDA). The panellists included Prof. Zbigniew Błocki (Director of National Science Centre), Prof. Hanna Bojar (Deputy Director of the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology of the Polish Academy of Sciences), Prof. Mirosława Grabowska (Director of CBOS, the Public Opinion Research Center) and Prof. Przemysław Urbańczyk (Director of the Polish Institute of Advanced Studies of the Polish Academy of Sciences, Polish member of the ESFRI Strategy Working Group on Social and Cultural Innovation). The previous speakers were also invited to take part in the round table: Ron Dekker (Director of CESSDA ERIC), Piotr Filipkowski (Head of ADJ), and Marcin W. Zieliński (Head of PADS).

The panellists received three questions before the event. They were given 2-3 minutes to answer a question of their choice based on their expertise.

Questions to the panellists

The Open Science and openness of research data are important drivers for innovative science policies in the EU. This has important implications also for research on national levels. However, the issue of Open Research Data is not limited to securing the storage place and accessibility. If the data is of such great value, it means that it is also necessary to implement appropriate curation procedures and to consider which data, how and to whom

to make available. At the same time, it should be borne in mind that the investments into both, data production and archivation, are back as a result of the data use and the main goal is therefore to enable it. In the panel discussion, we would like to focus on the following issues:

1. What are the main opportunities and challenges in opening access to research data for your institution and/or for Polish research?
2. What should the landscape of Open Research Data infrastructure in Poland look like? What role should national e-infrastructures play, what individual research institutions and universities and which way the national domain specific data archives such as PADS and ADJ can contribute to it?
3. How important do you consider the integration into the European landscape in this area? In this context, do you see a possible Polish membership in CESSDA ERIC and similar pan-European research infrastructures as beneficial and desirable?

Report on the round table discussion

In Poland, starting from this year, publications resulting from publicly funded research have to be openly accessible, via open access publishing or through repositories. About 3 years ago, data management plans were introduced by NCN, the main research funder. All speakers were in favour of data sharing. They saw many opportunities but also some challenges to overcome. Then, the discussion focused on the manner to share research data. If most approved a national infrastructure (or several), others preferred an international solution.

Opportunities of sharing data

As for publications, several panellists stated that publicly funded research data should be publicly available, as this would be beneficial for Polish research and researchers. Indeed, collecting data in social sciences (both regarding the qualitative and quantitative approach) is expensive in terms of time and financial resources, as well as knowledge needed for example on survey methodology. Data are thus "inaccessible" for average researchers. Sharing research data broadens the access to data and facilitates research for individual researchers. Indeed, researchers can carry out new analyses and formulate new interpretations. They can analyse unique data that cannot be collected again, compare data across time and contexts to address complex questions. Sharing research data allows also to verify and reproduce research analysis. It also enables future use of data and increases networking and exchanges between researchers.

Challenges

One of the main challenges raised by the panellists is the lack of data sharing culture among the Polish research community. Researchers are often very possessive with the data they collected. They must understand the benefits of open science, and change their practice from storing data to sharing data. To achieve that an important task is to raise awareness. Incentives to convince researchers to share data are also needed, as well as information and trainings on sharing data. Researchers should know that archiving data does not mean to open every data for everyone, but that access to personal data could be restricted to some type of users or usages. Moreover, preparing data and documentation that allow secondary users to understand and analyse them properly is costly in terms of time. As a consequence of data sharing requirements, funded research projects should receive money devoted to the preparation of data and documentation for archiving and sharing purposes.

A second type of challenges concerned the development of appropriate infrastructures and policies, as well as the legislative and ethical aspects. A last type of challenges referred to technical concerns related to the digitalization of data, the diversity of data forms and formats, the increasing diversity of data types (e.g. from the Internet).

Making data available in Poland

To overcome these challenges, the panellists stated several conditions on data sharing in repositories. The repositories' activities should aim at building reputation and trust within the research community. For this purpose, the terms of use should be precisely defined, data security and compliance with FAIR principles ensured, the metadata indexed in relevant databases, and training for researchers should be provided. High-level standards should be maintained. Data must be deposited in repositories that satisfy requirements and have a seal, they must comply with the policies. The awareness of the scientists, the community and decision makers is more important to be sure that data resulting from publicly funded projects are available freely and not as part of paywalls. Poland is at the beginning of this process.

One panellist acknowledged the good work of the Polish data archives for social sciences in providing access to research data and declared that their institution would transfer their datasets to them. Another panellist regretted that the Polish archives "contained just a couple of outdated files". The head of ADJ explained that there were currently 30 qualitative datasets, which was good for a young archive.

Then discussion concentrated on whether the data archives should be integrated into a national infrastructure or if Polish data should be shared in an international data repository. First, a panellist reminded the audience that many repositories have emerged over the past decade, but they have been created as part of research projects, with time-limited funding.

Stable long-term funding is thus needed to ensure that repositories plan and undertake systematic activities. There is a need to develop a strategy for long-term institutional and financial support for open social data repositories that would include long-term solutions for long-term archiving, and the development of IT technologies and tools. Other panellists were rather in favour of a more international approach also for the social sciences and favoured storing the data in an international repository. Another panellist explained that when Polish data were stored in ICPSR (before having local archives), most users were from abroad and not from Poland as Polish institutions could not pay the yearly membership fee to access the data. Nobody knows better the data produced in a particular country than researchers from this country. For this panellist, the system that consists of two levels: data archived in local repositories, but available from a pan-European data catalogue (e.g., CESSDA data catalogue) is a good solution.

Finally, there was a discussion regarding which data should be shared. For some panellists, public organisations should be obliged to share the data collected with public money on a data archive. For others, not all data should be publicly available, but there should be a reason for not publishing the data (such as privacy, security, etc.).

Integration in the EU landscape

The vision of most panellists is that Poland membership in pan European infrastructures would be valuable, beneficial, and desirable. Data from Poland should be accessible internationally and Polish researchers should have access to international data to perform comparative analyses.

Polish repositories need to collect social science data and provide access to them in accordance with European and international standards. Polish data archives should thus maintain a close cooperation with international institutions. For several panellists, CESSDA provides high standards for such cooperation. This would provide new possibilities and new perspectives.

Minutes of the afternoon session

The CESSDA Data Day's afternoon session was a workshop on managing research data in social sciences in Poland. It was held in Polish from 13:30 to 17:00.

13:30 – 14:15: Part I. Introduction to research data management and sharing

The first part of the workshop was conducted by Wojciech Fenrich (Open Science Platform, Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling, University of Warsaw). Dr Fenrich began with the definitions and types of research data and presented

benefits from correct data management. Then, he discussed elements of data management plans, as well as requirements formulated in the Horizon 2020 programme and National Science Centre in Poland (NCN) guidelines, considering the FAIR principles. Finally, he presented valuable materials and tools to facilitate data management (e.g., CESSDA DMEG, DMP Tool, DMP Online). After his talk, time for discussion was scheduled, but there was no question from the audience.

14:15 – 15:15: Part II. Research data in social sciences

The second part of the workshop was prepared by Danuta Życzyńska-Ciołek and Magdalena Bielińska (Institute of Philosophy and Sociology, Polish Academy of Sciences) together with Marcin Zieliński (Polish Social Data Archive; Robert Zajonc Institute for Social Studies, University of Warsaw). It concerned the selection and preparation of social data for sharing and the presentation of Social Data Repository⁴, a platform to share quantitative and qualitative data. The presenters answered two questions from participants: 1) on the availability of additional materials, especially the video guide to the repository; 2) about setting the embargo period.

15:30 – 17:00: Part III. Legal aspects of sharing research data

The last part of the workshop was given by Krzysztof Siewicz (Open Science Platform, Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling, University of Warsaw). It concerned research data as a subject of legal regulation, its sharing from the perspectives of intellectual property rights and personal data protection (also in terms of ethical codes), and possibilities to apply free licences. One of the participants asked Dr Siewicz about the possibility of contact to consult legal complexities in the future.

Demands for local events

Among the six applicants for the CESSDA Mentorship Programme 2020, four (67%) wanted to organise a local event in their country with CESSDA participation to raise awareness to funders and researchers, which is exactly the aim of the local event concept developed within this task. This very high demand's rate shows the need for organising such local events by CESSDA partners.

⁴ <https://rds.icm.edu.pl> (accessed on 13.04.2021)

Conclusion

Overall, the CESSDA local event in Poland was a success as it reached a wide audience among researchers from different research institutions in social sciences and other research fields. ADJ and PADS, the Polish archives for respectively qualitative and quantitative social science data, had the opportunity to present their services to 66 participants, composed of potential data depositors and data users, as well as data librarians and representatives of different research institutions' management. In the afternoon, 35 participants took part in the data management and data sharing training prepared by three Polish research institutions (ICM, IFiS PAN and PADS).

In the morning session, the EU research landscape was presented and the importance for a country such as Poland to get organised in order to join ERICs and EOSC was reminded. During the round table, most panellists supported the need for national social science data archives in Poland, but the discussion also brought out a misapprehension about the specificities of social sciences data compared to data in other research fields (e.g., in terms of data collection, management, preservation and dissemination, notably about ethics and anonymisation). This reveals the importance of gathering together researchers, data professionals and funders from different fields.

Indeed, such events give the opportunity to inform all relevant stakeholders in a country about social sciences specific needs in terms of data preservation and dissemination and to present the archiving services and activities already available. The presence of CESSDA surely provides extra strength to the position of local data archives and helps to convince some representatives to join the round table. This is certainly the reason why local events are so in demand at CESSDA partners and why CESSDA should continue to organise such local events. Moreover, the round table, which is at the centre of the event, allows for representatives of different institutions – sometimes also coming from different academic fields – to discuss together the specific topic of data preservation and dissemination for social sciences and how they envisioned organising and funding it in their country. This could be the first time these representatives, and thus their institutions, meet and discuss this topic together. If this is the case, the local organisers should take this opportunity to follow up contacts and negotiations with these stakeholders. Therefore, if new local events are envisioned, the 2020 team strongly encourages future teams to use the general concept presented in this document, which places the round table at the centre of the event but is also flexible enough to answer specific needs.

Finally, the timing of the local event is also important for its success, as mentioned by Marcin W. Zieliński, head of PADS:

“CESSDA Data Day 2021 which was held in March 2021 in Poland was a fully successful event. For the first time Polish research community in the field of social sciences had the opportunity to meet representatives of the European research community active in the field of social research data archiving. The event also included a workshop on preparation of the data management plan and legal issues related to archiving, licensing and sharing research data. Data archiving matters are very topical nowadays in Poland, as sharing and archiving data is obligatory since last year due to the requirements of public institutions financing science. This fact was emphasised by the Director of National Science Center who also participated in the CESSDA Data Day event alongside high-level representatives of the Polish Academy of Sciences and Public Opinion Research Center on the Polish side.”